

**BODY-SATISFACTION AS A FACTOR OF INVOLVEMENT IN
FITNESS PRACTICES.****Dekhkonboeva Zulayxo Dilshod qizi**

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Annotation: The individual's attitude to physical activity is formed in the socio-cultural context. In the modern industrial society, with the improvement of mass communication technologies and the intensive development of the beauty industry, ideas about the superiority of beautiful people over ugly ones are actively postulated, unrealistic templates, standards and beliefs are imposed that success directly depends on appearance. This forces modern people to make more and more demands on their appearance, and therefore the percentage of men and women who are dissatisfied with their own appearance is growing. The article presents the problems of studying psychological factors of involvement in fitness practices. Two directions of studying involvement in fitness practices are considered: motivational factors and personal factors: 1) search for the main motivating motives for applying to training; 2) identification of the relationship of motivating motives for applying to training with the real perception of one's own body and satisfaction with one's own appearance. The article reveals the results of studying the behavior associated with involvement in fitness practices.

Keywords: fitness practices, engagement, motivational factors, physicality, satisfaction with one's own appearance.

Introduction. In psychological science, questions of physical activity are revealed through the concepts of attitude to sports, physical culture, involvement in the culture of fitness. When discussing fitness culture, they emphasize the positive (constructive physical activity) and negative (race for new beauty standards, eating disorders) features of its impact on the mental health of the individual.

The results of research indicate that due to self-objectification, women have increased anxiety about appearance, dissatisfaction with body image, a sense of shame, decreased self-esteem of body image and overall self-esteem, increased symptoms of food disorders, and increased depressiveness (Labunskaya V. A. 2010)

The purpose of this article is to provide a deeper scientific and research understanding of the psychological mechanisms of involvement in fitness practices by discussing the results of research on motivational and personal determinants of involvement in fitness practices and considering the data of empirical measurement of attitude to the body and self-assessment of the body image of the Self.

Literature review. In psychological science, questions of physical activity are revealed through the concepts of attitude to sports, physical culture, involvement in the culture of fitness. When discussing fitness culture, they emphasize the positive (constructive physical activity) and negative (race for new beauty standards, eating disorders) features of its impact on the mental health of the individual.

In psychology, the methodological basis of research on the issue of corporeality is the cultural and historical theory of L. S. Vygotsky, which contributed to a qualitative change in the general ideas about human bodily development in both normal and abnormal currents. The implementation of the principles of the cultural-historical approach involves the study of psychological phenomena in a culturological context. There is a possibility that deviation from the cultural path of development is one of the main sources of psychological disorders of the body image, as well as psychosomatic disorders.

A special place in psychological research of the Self-body is occupied by the topic of "psychology of corporeality". The problems of this area of psychological knowledge can be attributed to the "eternal" problems that have always interested humanity. The knowledge and experience gained in this area is of great scientific and practical interest. The central issue in understanding the category of "corporeality" is the interaction between the "soul and body", the relationship between the physical and the spiritual. Initially, in social and humanitarian knowledge, there is a dilution, an opposition of the concepts of "soul" and "body" (Zinchenko V. P. 2007, p 8,) In order to overcome it, the category of "corporeality" was proposed as a special phenomenon that occupies, according to V. P. Zinchenko, the space "between" the soul and the body, "...in which there was it would be something that applies equally to the soul and the body, but it would be neither. Or, more precisely, it would be the flesh of both the soul and the body. Living movement is at least an intermediary between the soul and the body" [Zinchenko V. P. 2007 p. 22]. Corporeality is the spiritualized body, i.e., the visible and experienced part of the soul.

In psychological science, involvement in fitness practices is studied within the framework of social psychology of health as a component of a healthy lifestyle and in connection with self-efficacy, the locus of health control (for example, M. Kh.Karamyan, 2007, 2010). From the point of view of health psychology, it is interesting to note the idea of J. R. R. Tolkien. Thomson et al. suggest that dissatisfaction with the body image and concern about it in the range from low to medium continuum levels can be useful, as it leads to "healthy" eating patterns and physical exercises(Thomson J.K. 2002 p. 142).

Questions of self-attitude are considered in the framework of psychological concepts of the individual's attitude to himself (V. V. Stolin, S. R. Pantileev, N. I. Sarjveladze). There is a consideration of the issue of changing self-attitude as a result of the inclusion of the individual in the "World of fitness culture" (V. N. Myasishchev's concept of personality as a system of relations 1996).

In psychological science, you can find many approaches to studying what different authors can refer to in different ways: body image, physicality, Self-physical, body concept, body diagram, appearance, etc. In foreign psychology, the most commonly used concept at present is the "body image". We can note the lack of a single definition and the presence of many theoretical concepts and approaches to the interpretation of the concept of "body image" (in Russian psychology, the concept of "I-physical" is often used, etc.) (Borilkevich V. E. 2003 , p. 45).

The concept of body image characterizes a person's perception of their appearance, including its subjective assessment, perception of their own body, attitudes and beliefs related to the body, the idea of an ideal body, affective and behavioral reactions. Most studies are devoted to the evaluation component of body image, namely dissatisfaction with the body (negative body image), since satisfaction with one's own appearance is associated with the psychological well-being of an individual.

The formation of body image is influenced by social factors and individual characteristics of a person (psychological and biological). Research confirms the significant role of social factors in the formation of a negative body image . In modern Western culture, there are certain standards (standards) in relation to appearance: for women, this is a slender and ageless body and attractiveness. Since the standards of beauty broadcast in Western society are unattainable for the majority, and the pressure of society to achieve the ideal is high, a situation of high risk of developing a negative body image is created . The adoption of a cultural standard of beauty as an internal standard that must be met (internalization) is a risk factor for developing dissatisfaction with the body(Tarkhanova P. M.,Kholmogorova A.B. 2011, p. 42).

V. A. Labunskaya contrasts cases when designing one's own external appearance is aimed at achieving compliance with social norms and patterns, and cases when it is caused by a conscious desire to embody one's own individuality, using external transformation to influence one's internal characteristics, value-semantic interpretations of oneself and another (Labunskaya V. A. 2010, p.30).

V. Nikolaeva notes that physicality turned out to be "theoretically invisible" for psychology, despite its obvious nature. Declaring the psychosomatic unity of man, psychology deals mainly with the phenomena of consciousness, higher mental activity, and physicality remains for it an alien, naturally organized and naturally ready-to-live quality. The concept of "corporeality" is used as a psychological opposition to the identity of "body-organism", and the phenomena of corporeality are considered as manifestations of communication and self-expression stereotypes (Nikolaeva V.V., Arina G.A 1996, p.12).

Currently, fitness classes are becoming a mass social phenomenon. Every day, more and more people turn to health-improving physical culture, which some authors also refer to as fitness (Bykhovskaya I. M., 2007 p.47).

Visitors to fitness centers turn to training for various reasons. The most common motivations for training are to maintain physical fitness, improve health, reduce excess weight, get rid of "negative energy", spend free time and find new acquaintances. But in the first place are the motives associated with the standards and expectations of a person's appearance and physical appearance. These standards and expectations, as well as a variety of methods that contribute to their achievement (diet, fitness, beauty products, etc.), are a kind of cultural ideals that are transmitted by modern society through the media.

R. Burns singled out the body image as one of the sources of the development of the Self-concept of personality. Based on F.'s ideas. Schonfeld and continuing the tradition of the "congruent" approach of K. Rogers, he spoke about the combination of psychological factors that influence the structure of body image. These include:

1. Real perception of external corporeality, based on its functional abilities.
2. Interiorized psychological factors that arise as a result of emotional experiences and various life situations of an individual.
3. Sociological factors: the reaction of others to an individual's appearance and body image and their interpretation of these reactions.

4. The ideal image of the body that arises as a result of generalizing the individual's attitude to his body, which arises as a result of specific observations, comparisons and identifications with the bodily qualities of other people (Thomson J.K. 2002, p . 58).

Research methodology. The methodological basis of this study was: the systematic biopsychosocial approach of J. R. R. Tolkien.Angel; V. N. Myasishchev's theory of relations; anthropological and humanistic approaches to understanding health; basic provisions of the psychology of corporeality.

The study involved 200 respondents, including 120 women and 80 men. The minimum age of respondents was – 18 years, and the maximum age was 45.

The entire sample was divided by age group (Table 1).2.2.1).

Table 1

Age characteristics of the study participants, %

Age groups	N	%
18-25 years	84	42.5
25-35 years	95	47.5
35-45 years	20	10
Total	200	100.0

As can be seen from Table 1, most of our sample consists of participants in the age group from 25-35 years. The average age of the study participants was 26 ± 0.77 .

To study motivational determinants, we used the Self – efficacy Scale (R. Schwarzer, M. Jerusalem), attitudes to the body – the Multicomponent questionnaire of attitude to one's own body (MBSRQ) by T. Cash, self – assessment of the body image of the Self-the method of studying self -attitude by V. Stolin, involvement -the author's questionnaire "Studying involvement in fitness practices".

Descriptive statistics, frequency analysis, the Mann-Whitney U-test for comparative analysis of two independent groups, and the binomial test for comparing two proportions were used as statistical processing methods. Statistical data processing was performed using the SPSS 26.0 and Minitab software.

Research results and their discussion. Fitness has clearly become an integral part of a person's life and is now more tightly integrated into the lexicon and even into the consciousness of a person. Physical activity and proper nutrition are clearly important components of healthy behavior.

The study of involvement in fitness practices was carried out using the author's questionnaire "Study of involvement in fitness practices". Analysis of the results showed that the majority of our sample in terms of the cognitive component of the methodology for studying involvement in fitness practices have sufficient knowledge about the types of fitness practices(68%), show interest in the topic of fitness in social networks (68.8%), are aware of the existence of fitness marathons and have an idea of the benefits of adequate involvement in fitness practices(72.5%).

Analyzing the data obtained on the emotional component, we can say that the study sample is distinguished by the presence of anticipation of the opportunity to engage in fitness(70%), the majority of study participants feel a surge of energy after fitness classes and note that fitness is a good way to relieve emotional tension, while they feel sad if they have to skip training(77%).

Based on the responses received on the behavioral component of the methodology for studying involvement in fitness practices, it can be concluded that most of the sample regularly practices fitness(57.5%), adheres to the norms of proper nutrition(44.5%). Most of the study participants independently plan their fitness program and monitor the regularity of meeting their fitness goals (49%).

For study The Self-efficacy Scale was used self-efficacy Schwarzer, M. Jerusalem. This technique allows you to assess the strength of an individual's faith in their ability to respond to difficult situations when it is necessary to cope with

difficulties. So, in general, the sample is dominated by participants with a high level of self-efficacy (57.5%).

A comparative analysis of differences in fitness practice engagement rates by self-efficacy level revealed statistically significant differences in the cognitive component ($U=2972,000$, $p<0.05$), emotional component ($U=1590,500$, $p<0.05$), behavioral component ($U=2856,500$, $p<0.05$), and engagement severity ($U=1907,500$, $p<0.05$). Thus, we can say that the respondents have sufficient knowledge about fitness practices, the results of fitness training inspire them to achieve higher goals, and they independently regulate the intensity of exercise in fitness.

Table 2

Differences in engagement indicators by level of self-efficacy, N=200

Scales	Average rank		Mann-Whitney criterion	Significance level (p)
	Low level N=85	High level N=115		
Cognitive component	77.96	117.16	2972,000,000	*
Emotional component	61.71	129.17	1590,500,000	*
Behavioral component	76.61	118.16	2856,500,000	*
Engagement	rate 65.44	126.41	1907,500,000	*

Note: * statistically significant differences are noted

The correlation analysis showed positive results of the self-efficacy indicator with indicators of cognitive ($r_s=0.325$, $p<0.01$), emotional ($r_s=0.656$, $p<0.01$), behavioral component ($r_s=0.385$, $p<0.01$) and involvement severity ($r_s=0.502$, $p<0.01$).

To study the questions of attitude to one's own physicality as a predictor of involvement in fitness practice, we used a multicomponent questionnaire of attitude to one's own body (MBSRQ) T.1. The analysis of differences in engagement indicators

from the level of body satisfaction found significant differences on the following scales: "cognitive component" ($U=2645,000$, $p<0.05$), "emotional component" ($U=2697,500$, $p<0.05$), "behavioral component" ($U=3485,500$, $p<0.05$), and "overall engagement score" ($U=2733,000$, $p<0.05$). It follows that participants with lower satisfaction with their appearance are more likely to show a high interest in the topic of fitness, regularly engage in fitness, they experience an emotion of sadness if fitness practices do not give the desired result, and have a higher rate of involvement in fitness practices.

Analysis of correlations between engagement indicators and satisfaction levels revealed the following statistically significant relationships. Thus, the scale "orientation to appearance" has a significant negative correlation with the scale "behavioral component" ($r_s=-0.346$, $p<0.05$). This allows us to say that excessive preoccupation with appearance contributes negatively to actions that promote regular fitness activities.

It should be noted that the scale "assessment of appearance" positively correlates with all scales of the methodology for studying involvement in fitness practices, namely the scales "cognitive component" ($r_s=0.604$, $p<0.05$), "emotional component" ($r_s=0.711$, $p<0.05$), "behavioral component" ($r_s=0.350$, $p<0.05$) and "engagement rate" ($r_s=0.623$, $p<0.05$). It follows that a high assessment of respondents' appearance affects the degree of involvement in the respondents' fitness practices.

Next, we will pay attention to the consideration of differences in the indicators of involvement from self-attitude. For this purpose, the method of studying самооотношения V. Stolin's self-attitude was used. Based on the data obtained (Table 3.3.5), we can see that the jackal "S integral feeling" for "or" "against" its own "I" ($U=1849,000$, $p<0.05$), "self-esteem" ($U=3718,000$, $p<0.05$), "autosympathy" ($U=2839,000$, $p<0.05$), "expecting positive attitude from others" ($U=3125,000$, $p<0.05$), "attitude of others" ($U=3397,500$, $p<0.05$), "self-guidance, self-consistency" ($U=3437,500$, $p<0.05$), and "self-blame" ($U=2455,000$, $p<0.05$) have statistically

significant differences in the indicators. Participants who strive to regularly apply fitness practices in life seek to gain positive treatment from others.

Conclusions and prospects of the study. Thus, leading in the structure of the cognitive component of involvement in fitness practice is the participants' understanding of the consequences of lack of fitness in life, emotional – negative experiences from irregular classes and skipping training, behavioral-independent planning of the training program and ensuring the regularity of fitness classes. The level of involvement in fitness practices depends on the characteristics of body satisfaction and self-attitude. This study does not claim to fully cover the problem of studying this topic, but is of a search nature. We believe that the problem under study has broad prospects for further scientific and empirical development and necessarily raises new questions related to the search for psychological (motivational-personal and socio-psychological) targets for conducting psychoeducational work with people with destructive involvement in fitness or with people with insufficient motivation for physical activity in order to maintain health.

List of literature

1. Borilkevich V. E. On Identification of Conceptthe concept "Fitness" / V. E. Borilkevich // Theory and practice of physical culture. 2003. No. 2. pp. 45-47.
2. Bykhovskaya I. M. Aksiologiya telesnosti i zdorov'e: svyazhennost' v kul'turologicheskom izmerenii [Axiology of corporeality and health: conjugation in the cultural dimension]. Psikhologiya telesnosti mezhdudushoy i telume [Psychology of corporeality between the soul and the body], MOSCOW: ACT, 2007, pp. 53-66
3. Durneva M. Yu., Meshkova, T. A. the Influence of socio-cultural standards of attractiveness on the formation of attitudes to the body and feeding behavior of adolescent girls and youth age // Psychological science and education. 2013. Volume 18. No. 2. pp. 25-34.

4. Zinchenko V. P. Psychology on the swing between the soul and the body / V. P. Zinchenko; ed. - comp. V. P. Zinchenko, T. S. Levi / / Psychology of corporeality between the soul and the body. - M.: ACT; ACT MOSCOW. - 2007. - pp. 5-52.
5. Karamyan M. Kh. Healthy behavior: definition and socio-psychological factors//Bulletin of NUUZ, 2007, no. 1, pp. 86-94; Karamyan M. H. Psikhologiya zdorovya [Psychology of health]. Educational and methodical manual. Tashkent: Mumtoz soz, 2010.
6. Labunskaya V. A." Vidimy chelovek " kak sotsial'no-psikhologicheskii fenomen ["Visible man" as a socio-psychological phenomenon]. 2010. No. 1. pp. 26-37.
7. Nikolaeva V. V., Arina G. A. From traditional psychosomatics to the psychology of corporeality // Vestn. Mosk. univ. Ser. 14.Psikhologiya [Psychology]. 1996. №2. C.8-18.
8. Tarkhanova P. M., Kholmogorova A. B. Sotsial'nye i psikhologicheskie faktory fizicheskogo perfekcionizma i unsatisfactoriness svoi telyu [Social and psychological factors of physical perfectionism and dissatisfaction with one's body]. - 2011. - No. 5. - p. 52-60.
9. Kholmogorova A. B. Physical perfectionism as a factor of affective spectrum disorders in modern culture / A. B. Kholmogorova, A. A. Dadeko // Medical psychology in Russia. 2010. № 3.
10. Stice E., Gau J.M., Rohde P. et al. Risk factors that predict future onset of each DSM–5 eating disorder: Predictive specificity in high-risk adolescent females // Journal of Abnormal Psychology. 2017. Vol. 126. № 1. P. 38–51.
11. Thomson J.K. Measuring Body image attitudes among adolescents and adults / J.K. Thomson, P. Van den Berg // in T.F. Cash and T. Pruzinsky (eds.). Body Image: A Handbook of Theory, Research and Clinical Practice. London: The Guilford Press, 2002. P. 142–153.